

Dielectric Polarisation of Binary Mixture

A. N. Srivastava and P. R. Talesara

Dielectric polarisation of nitrobenzene has been studied at 30° in three solvents benzene, carbon tetrachloride and cyclohexane. The results obtained have been discussed to understand the merits of the equation proposed by Palit¹ and also to study the molecular interaction in the light of Earp and Glasstone theory².

The equations which have been in frequent use to evaluate the orientation polarisation and then to calculate the solution moment value, are due to Hedestrand³, Hoecker⁴, Halverstadt and Kumler⁵, Le Fevre and Vine⁶. These authors have obtained their results under a few assumptions. Recently Palit¹ has proposed a method through the concept of specific polarisation involving no assumption.

Therefore the dielectric polarisation of nitrobenzene, though studied earlier^{7,8} has been determined with a view to examine the merits of the equation proposed by Palit¹ and also to understand the applicability of Earp and Glasstone theory² to study the molecular interaction in a binary mixture.

EXPERIMENTAL

The practical work essentially involves the measurements of dielectric constant, refractive index and density of various solutions containing different mole fractions of the solute. The method and technique of measuring these physical quantities have been described in the earlier paper.⁹

Nitrobenzene of B.D.H. grade was purified by distilling twice in a quickfit apparatus and the fraction boiling between 208°-209° was used. Benzene and carbon tetrachloride of E. Merck (G. R.) were used as such as their dielectric constants were found to be in fair agreement with those cited in the literature¹⁰. Cyclohexane of B.D.H. grade was distilled in the quickfit apparatus and the fraction at 79° was used.

1. Santi R. Palit, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 3952.
2. D. P. Earp and S. Glasstone, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1709.
3. G. Hedestrand, *Z. Physik. Chem.* 1929, **B 2**, 428.
4. F. E. Hoecker, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1936, **4**, 431.
5. Halverstadt and Kumler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 2988.
6. Le Fevre and Vine, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1805.
7. H. O. Jenkins, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 480.
8. B. Krishna and K. K. Srivastava, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1957, **27**, 835.
9. A. N. Srivastava and P. R. Talesara, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971 **48**, 359.
10. C. N. R. Rao, "A Hand book of Chemistry and Physics", (1967).

Palit¹ has suggested the evaluation of specific orientation polarisation from the relation

$$p_2 = \frac{3(\epsilon_1 - n_1^2)}{d_1(\epsilon_1 + 2)(n_1^2 + 2)} \left(1 - \frac{\beta_0}{d_1}\right) + \frac{3\alpha_0}{d_1(\epsilon_1 + 2)^2} - \frac{6n_1\gamma_0}{d_1(n_1^2 + 2)^2}$$

where α_0 , β_0 and γ_0 are respectively the concentration coefficients at infinite dilution of dielectric constant, density and refractive index. Specific polarisation p_2 , when multiplied by the molecular weight of the solute gives the molecular orientation polarisation (P_{2M}), which is used to determine the dipole moment value from the relation

$$\mu = 0.01281 \times 10^{-18} \times P_{2M} T^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

This value has been further compared and confirmed by evaluating the solution moment from $(P_{2\infty} - Pe)$, $P_{2\infty}$ (the solute polarisation at infinite dilution) has been calculated by the method of Halverstadt and Kumler⁵. Electronic polarisation Pe is the same as the molecular refraction for the sodium D line and has been taken from the literature¹⁰. Atomic polarisation has not been considered according to the suggestion of Debye¹¹ viz. the electronic polarisation calculated from sodium D line partly compensates the neglect of atomic polarisation.

TABLE 1

Nitrobenzene in Benzene

$$n_1 = 1.4960 \quad d_1 = 0.86790 \quad \epsilon_1 = 2.2686$$

	$f_2 \times 10^2$	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	n_{12}	P_{12}	P_2	$PE(\text{Excess polarisation})$
1.	0.1968	2.3011	0.86904	1.4965	27.221	267.597	+0.341
2.	0.3931	2.3388	0.86998	1.4965	27.726	288.517	+0.752
3.	0.5904	2.4038	0.87054	1.4970	28.700	357.537	+1.552
4.	0.7954	2.4455	0.87102	1.4970	29.293	346.837	+2.005
5.	0.9835	2.4843	0.87150	1.4970	29.833	340.537	+2.420
6.	1.9573	2.7075	0.87518	1.4975	32.701	330.937	+4.622
7.	2.8671	2.9144	0.87886	1.4980	35.193	321.327	+6.496
8.	3.6400	3.0958	0.88196	1.4985	37.188	313.587	+7.965
					$P_2 = 372.40$ cc.		$\alpha_0 = 14.6660$
					$Pe = 32.59$ cc.		$\beta_0 = 0.24210$
					$\mu = 4.11$ D		$\gamma_0 = 0.03778$

TABLE 2

Nitrobenzene in CCl₄

$f_2 \times 10^2$	ϵ_{12}	$n_1 = 1.4560$	$d_1 = 1.5739$	$\epsilon_1 = 2.2144$	P_2	PE (Excess polarisation)	
		d_{12}	n_{12}	P_{12}			
1.	0.1178	2.2464	1.5734	1.4565	28.695	477.236	+0.450
2.	0.3937	2.3000	1.5723	1.4565	29.555	380.966	+1.127
3.	0.6004	2.3382	1.5721	1.4570	30.151	358.786	+1.584
4.	0.7995	2.3856	1.5705	1.4570	30.897	369.746	+2.198
5.	0.9819	2.4181	1.5697	1.4575	31.395	357.016	+2.577
6.	1.9028	2.6120	1.5668	1.4585	34.190	344.756	+4.756
7.	2.8831	2.8129	1.5618	1.4595	36.891	330.796	+6.805
8.	3.7045	2.9926	1.5599	1.4610	39.070	322.516	+8.437

$P_2 = 372.77$ cc. $\alpha_0 = 25.9259$
 $Pe = 32.59$ cc. $\beta_0 = -0.5000$
 $\mu = 4.11$ D $\gamma_0 = +0.16239$

TABLE 3

Nitrobenzene in Cyclohexane

$f_2 \times 10^2$	ϵ_{12}	$n_1 = 1.4220$	$d_1 = 0.7673$	$\epsilon_1 = 1.9904$	P_2	PE (Excess polarisation)	
		d_{12}	n_{12}	P_{12}			
1.	0.2431	2.0370	0.76825	1.4225	28.157	266.167	+0.416
2.	0.4508	2.0678	0.76908	1.4230	28.769	291.997	+0.889
3.	0.6672	2.1032	0.77022	1.4230	29.454	308.897	+1.429
4.	0.8779	2.1397	0.77065	1.4235	30.170	322.937	+2.003
5.	1.1863	2.1973	0.77218	1.4240	31.242	336.517	+2.868
6.	2.0919	2.3525	0.77520	1.4250	34.044	336.717	+5.061
7.	3.0891	2.5299	0.77976	1.4260	36.952	331.067	+7.300
8.	3.8834	2.6640	0.78270	1.4270	39.029	332.477	+8.843

$P_2 = 384.92$ cc. $\alpha_0 = 11.8857$
 $Pe = 32.59$ cc. $\beta_0 = 0.27368$
 $\mu = 4.18$ D $\gamma_0 = 00.08750$

TABLE 4

Solvent	P_{2M}		μ_s			μ_v Dipole moment in vapour state
	Orientation polarisation		Dipole moment in solution			
	Halverstadt and Kumler	Palit	By Present authors		Earlier workers	
			Halverstadt and Kumler	Palit		
1. Benzene	339.81 cc	340.35 cc	4.11 D	4.11 D	4.11 D ¹²	
2. Carbon tetrachloride	340.18 cc	337.72 cc	4.11 D	4.09 D	4.05 D ¹²	4.22 D
3. Cyclohexane	352.33 cc	348.33 cc	4.18 D	4.16 D	4.09- 4.12 D ¹²	

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Molecular polarisation values 340.35 ml, 337.72 ml, and 348.33 ml of nitrobenzene at 30° in benzene, carbontetrachloride and cyclohexane respectively calculated by the equation of Palit¹ are comparable with the respective values 339.81 ml., 340.18 ml. and 352.33 ml determined by the method due to Halverstadt and Kumler⁵.

The apparent dipole moment value in all the three solvents are lower than $4.22 D^{12}$, a value in the vapour state since the actual sign of the solvent effect is negative, the actual value of μ_s observed in solution should be smaller in benzene than in cyclohexane, this fact is amply supported by our data (Table 4). Jenkins⁷ has also calculated the solution polarisation of nitrobenzene in cyclohexane having minimum concentration $0.02 f_2$. It is interesting to note that in a further diluted solution (as in our case) the increase in molecular polarisation with concentration suggests that there may be a tendency for end-on association. However our data in higher concentration than $0.01 f_2$ agree with the observation of Jenkins that solute polarisation increases with dilution.

To study the interaction in these solvents, the applicability of Earp and Glasstone theory has been examined. The curves $\left(\frac{\epsilon_{12}-1}{\epsilon_{12}+2} \right)^2 V_s P_{12}$ (Fig. 1) are linear, and hence shows that no chemical interaction is there. The values of P^E (the excess polarisation) in column 7th, being positive eliminates the possibility of dipole association as well. Except in cyclohexane the curves $P^E V_s f_1 f_2$ (Fig. 2) in benzene and carbon tetrachloride are linear

and pass through the origin. This suggests that charge transfer type complexes are formed in the latter two solvents. The specific interaction according to Goates and Sullivan¹³, in these solvents, appears to be of donor-acceptor type. In case of nitrobenzene in benzene, it is expected that nitrobenzene¹⁴ may function as an acceptor, accepting thereby π electrons of the benzene ring¹⁵ (donor). In carbon tetrachloride as solvent it is suggested, that the aromatic ring of nitrobenzene donates the π electrons (π bonding) to the empty 3d level of chlorine atoms in carbon tetrachloride. Praunitz and his coworkers¹⁶ have adduced evidence that carbon tetrachloride behaves as an electron acceptor. Recently¹⁷ the support for complex formation between benzene and carbon tetrachloride (acceptor) is also reported on the basis of far infrared spectroscopic measurements. In the present case, as $-\text{NO}_2$ group does not enhance the electron density of the ring, it is expected therefore that the stability of the nitrobenzene complex in carbon tetrachloride would be smaller than that of the benzene complex. The possibility of complex formation in cyclohexane does not arise as it has no π electrons. Our experimental data fully demonstrate these facts.

Table 4 contains the summarised data which exhibit that apparent dipole moment values calculated by us are in fair agreement with those cited in the literature¹².

13. J. R. Goates and R. J. Sullivan, *J. Phys. Chem.* Ithaca, 1959, **63**, 589.
14. A. H. Maki and D. H. Geske, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 1852.
15. H. M. Rosenberg and E. C. Eimutis, *J. Phys. Chem.* Ithaca, 1966, **70**, 3494.
16. R. Anderson and J. M. Praunitz, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, **39**, 1225.
17. G. W. Chantry et al., *Spectrochim Acta*, 1967, **23A**, 2749.

The authors are thankful to Prof. R. C. Kapoor, Head, Department of Chemistry for providing the necessary facilities. One of us (P.R.T.) is grateful to C.S.I.R. and U.G.C., Govt. of India for financing the project.

Department of Chemistry,
University of Jodhpur.
Jodhpur.

Received February 15, 1971